

EXTENSION OF THE PUBLICATION PARADIGM: THE TEXTILE COMPOSITES ARCHIVE

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SUMMARY

The multi-scale structure of textile composites causes significant complexity in numerical models, the predictions, and the phenomena observed during experiments. Only a small fraction of the details can be included in the framework of a scientific publication. The proposed Textile Composites Archive extends the publication paradigm by providing a mechanism for sharing all of the essential details.

Keywords: textile composites, computational models, experimental characterization, collaboration, data archive

INTRODUCTION

There is increasing interest in the use of textile composites in diverse applications. Optimal design and application of the materials requires that the behavior be predictable. The last two decades has seen a remarkable expansion in the literature on modeling of textile composites. Most of this work has focused on investigating the behavior of an infinite array of unit cells subjected to macroscopically constant strain and stress states. This is often referred to as unit cell analysis or periodic analysis. While early studies focused on predicting moduli and identifying that there were stress concentrations due to the undulations and interlacing, more recent studies have begun to explore progressive failure behavior, alternative ways to interpret the data, non-periodic

configurations (e.g. free edge effects and delamination) and questions about the sensitivity of the predictions to assumptions about the idealized geometry.

Both the analytical and experimental investigations have made it very clear that the geometric complexity and the concomitant complexity of the response present considerable challenges both in performing the studies and in conveying a summary of the efforts in a journal publication. Ideally, one beginning a new investigation should be able to build on what is in the literature to expedite the new study. Unfortunately, the complexity of even the simplest models of a plain weave composite are not simple. If symmetries are to be exploited, even the specification of appropriate boundary conditions is difficult. Trying to check one's work versus what is in the literature is not only difficult and time consuming, it is generally impossible to know if one is really analyzing the same configuration.

Experimentally characterizing damage initiation and growth in textile composites is complicated by the complex architecture. Even describing the tow architecture is difficult. A few micrographs of a "typical" cross-section to illustrate the architecture or damage are generally far from sufficient for knowing the geometric details that should be assumed in a model. Without extensive comparisons of analytical and experimental data, one runs the risk of producing pretty pictures of phenomena such as stress concentrations that are driven by artifacts of the assumptions made about the architecture. Similarly, without appropriate analytical models, it is easy to misinterpret experimentally observed phenomena. These are serious challenges to the development of reliable tools for predicting the behavior of textile composites.

These challenges were discussed at the symposium "Meso-FE Modelling of Textiles and Textile Composites" (St.-Petersburg, 2007). It was concluded that a mechanism of sharing research data that goes beyond journal publications was needed. The conventional journal format is incompatible with the complexity of data being generated by both experiments and three-dimensional analyses of textile composites. At best a journal paper describes a few insights distilled from extensive data. Often there is insufficient information to replicate the models even if one did have the time and tools necessary, which is seldom the case. The proposed archive is not intended to replace journal papers, but to provide enhanced access to experimental and simulation data. The following sections describe the intended scope of the archive, how it is organized, a brief description of the current contents, and finally a few summary remarks.

Scope of Archive

The goal of the archive is to provide data that will expedite the development of validated tools for predicting the behavior of textile composites. Of course, this is also the goal of journal publications. The difference is that the archive is not limited to brief summaries. Since computer disk space has become so inexpensive, the archive will provide details about experiments and analyses that permit convenient re-use of the results for various purposes, such as

- Evaluation of existing or new techniques for analysis of textile composites.
- Performance of parametric studies that go beyond the tools available to and time constraints of a single organization.
- Examination of the raw data with new perspectives/ideas not anticipated when the simulations or experiments were conducted.

The archive extends the "lifetime" of the raw data and makes it available to a broad "virtual" research group.

It would be naïve to assume that we can anticipate the most useful data to be in the archive. The nature of the contents will evolve over time. However, the initial emphasis will be on

- Experimental results that can be used to validate finite element models that directly model the tow architecture.
- Complete input and output data for finite element models of various textile composites.
- Benchmarks such as predicted stress distributions as a function of mesh refinement.

The following phenomena will also be emphasized initially:

- Deformability of dry textile reinforcements (biaxial tension, shear, compression).
- Flow through textile reinforcements during processing, including the effects of preform distortion.
- Mechanical behavior of textile composites in quasi-static loading.

This archive is intended to be an extension of the conventional publication paradigm, not a replacement. Accordingly, citations for publications related to the data will be provided. These publications can serve to give some perspective on what has been done and also what new investigations might be needed. Also, as useful links to related sites are identified, these will be included in the archive.

A later section in this paper will give some details about the current contents of the archive in the hopes of both attracting attention to the archive, but also to inspire suggestions for improvement.

Organization of Archive

The Textile Composites Archive is currently hosted at Texas A&M University. The link is <http://textilecomposite.tamu.edu>. To simplify the maintenance of the archive, each contributor will be provided with a directory where he/she has total freedom organizing the contributions. A link will be provided from the main page to a web page in each of these directories. Also, each contributor will maintain backups of his/her contributions. This will provide redundancy in the system. Although parts of the site may be password protected if necessitated by the nature of the data, the primary mission of the archive is to provide open access to extensive data. To access the protected areas, one would contact the owner of the data directly via a link provided on the site. In order to become a contributor to the archive, one should contact John Whitcomb at jdw@tamu.edu or Stepan Lomov at Stepan.Lomov@mtm.kuleuven.be.

CURRENT CONTENTS

This section describes some of the initial contributions by the authors of this paper. In addition to giving brief descriptions of data, there are also suggestions about how this data could be used by others. This section is divided according to the contributing institution.

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

At this stage, K.U.Leuven provides two clusters of data for the database: 1) Finite element models accompanied by experimental study of damage accumulation in various textile composites and 2) Test finite element problems.

The primary goal of structural meso-scale analysis is to predict the mechanical behavior of a part based on internal geometry. When comparing experimental data, it is important to distinguish between the physical effects, imposed by production technique and chemical compositions of the matrix, on the one hand and the architecture induced effects on the other hand. The first contribution of K.U.Leuven is data on damage accumulation in various textile architectures made of the same epoxy matrix, and using the same RTM production technique, but with the wide range of architectures. Four carbon-epoxy materials are presented: *braided*, *satin woven*, *non-crimp fabric (NCF)* and *quasi-unidirectional composites*. Two of these architectures are discussed below. Results for the braided composite have been presented in previous publications [1-3]. The tensile tests are accompanied by acoustic emission registration, surface strain measurements, and post-mortem X-Ray crack observations at different load levels [4]. The comparison of various materials allows for clear distinction between non-linearity imposed by different deformation and failure mechanisms, such as intra-ply matrix cracking and plasticity. The experimental data for the composites is accompanied by a tensile diagram of the pure matrix. The following briefly describes the data that will be provided for the non-crimp fabric composites and the quasi-unidirectional composites.

Carbon-epoxy non-crimp fabric (NCF) composites

The bi-axial multi-ply carbon reinforcement fabrics (Figure 1a) are stitched by polyester (PES) yarns in a tricot pattern with an areal density of 6 g/m². The stitching has no other function but to bind the plies together. The pattern of polyester yarns induces long triangular distortions in plane of the textile [5]. The textiles are produced based on the UD plies with an areal density of ~150 g/m².

Figure 1. a) In plane geometry of the NCF and geometrical model of unit cells (produced in WiseTex [6]) b) FE models of the sheared and non-sheared NCF composites

To study the effect of draping on the mechanical properties, the biaxial fabrics are sheared at 30° and 50° (ply angles $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 20^\circ$ see Figure 1b). The tensile tests are performed both in the fibre and non-fibre directions (see Figure 2).

The FE models are found on a simplified presentation of the geometry [7]. The out-of-plane crimp/waviness of the plies is neglected. The stitching yarns are excluded for simplicity as far as their stiffness contribution is close to the one of the matrix. The

effect of the stitching is accounted for by introducing matrix resin rich zones and local variation of orientation and volume fraction of the fibres in the vicinity of distortion boundaries.

Figure 2. Tensile diagrams of $\pm 60^\circ$ and $\pm 70^\circ$ NCF composites (loading is in 0°). Non-linearity is attributed to intensive matrix intra-ply cracking

Figure 3. Geometry of quasi-UD composite: (a) in-plane image of the textile, (b) FE model of the textile reinforcement (produced in WiseTex [6])

Quasi-UD composite

Quasi-UD fabric (Figure 3) is produced by weaving flat UD carbon yarns with sparse, thin glass yarns in a plain (1×1) pattern. Areal density of the textile is 285 g/m^2 . The idea behind this architecture is to make a stable, non-crimp, drapable textile, which can be produced via RTM technology. Eight 10-ply laminates are tested along the carbon fibre direction (0°), and in the “non-standard” directions 30 , 45 , 60 , 90° . The geometrical model has been generated in WiseTex software [6] and meshed in MeshTex program (Osaka University) [8]. The study of damage in these composites has revealed a peculiar failure mode: occurrence of inter-yarn delaminations without primary intra-yarn matrix cracking. The damage is observed in the outer plies only.

The second contribution concerns imaginary architectures for verification of a new 2-scale modeling approach. The central issue of hierarchical methods is to effectively handle the two artificially separated scales, macro and meso, with the least possible computational cost. The common assumption is that a textile unit cell is representative in both the geometrical and mechanical senses. Being loaded with appropriate boundary conditions, it can reveal the meso stress distribution at any macro location.

Typically, a unit cell is postulated to be far away from the boundaries, both in the plane and in the thickness directions of composite, and to be surrounded by unit cells of the same geometry. These assumptions lead to so-called periodic or symmetric boundary

conditions. In reality, the presence of the free surface and the arbitrary stacking of plies in textile laminates leads up to a factor 2 difference of local stress in an idealized infinite and real laminates. Hence, the challenge is to construct boundary conditions for a single unit cell representing an interaction with an arbitrary stacked ply sequence. Novel boundary conditions need to be tested against a reference solution obtained for an entire laminate. 2D and 3D test problems are proposed in the second contribution.

The set of test problems includes 2D and 3D examples. The 2D ones present a cross-section of plain-weave textile laminate. For the 3D instance, a non-balanced twill woven laminate is employed as an illustration. The through-the-thickness columns of 6, 4 and 2 unit cells have been built for the reference solution. Three configurations have been prepared: (1) periodical, (2) step-wise shift, where all the even plies are in phase, and all the non-even plies are shifted to an equal length (the distance between two neighbouring weft yarns), (3) stairs-like shift, where every next ply is shifted to the same distance relative to the previous one in the same direction (see Figure 4). Every ply has an identical mesh pattern to ease the comparison of the results, and all the laminates possess a periodical node pattern on its opposite faces. The single ply unit cell contains 16,640 8-node brick elements. The reference FE models are submitted along with the FE model of a single unit cell.

Figure 4. FE models of the unit cell of twill woven laminate with two stacking sequences: step-like and stairs-like

These test problems invite for comparison of various 2-scale concepts and boundary conditions for textile composites [9].

Texas A&M University

Finite element models for a variety of weave architectures will be placed in the archive. Figure 5 shows schematics of some of the architectures. The behavior of these composites has been reported in many papers [10-18]. The data will include mesh files, complete input scripts, and results of elastic analyses. Documentation will be provided to describe the format for the input and output data. Most of the models will be for a unit cell or fraction of a unit cell representing a woven laminate that is infinite in all dimensions (i.e. periodic analysis). For the plain weave composite, a wide range of mesh refinements will be provided. Results for glass and graphite material systems, waviness ratios (the ratio of mat thickness to tow wavelength) of 1/3 and 1/9, and symmetrically and simply stacked laminates will be provided. Therefore, the archive will contain a wide spectrum of woven models available to collaborators for their study. This collection should also prove useful as benchmarks which can be compared with results from other studies. Some comparisons would be similar to an on-going round-robin study which should lead to new insights.

The archive will also serve to extend the amount of information presented in publications. For example, the archive will contain extensive data from a study on the effect of traction free surfaces on stresses in a carbon/epoxy plain weave composite [18]. Figure 6 shows the basic configuration, a unit cell for a four-ply symmetric laminate with traction free surfaces that is periodic only in the x_1 direction. For comparison, the paper also considered the periodic case. The journal paper discussed the normal interlaminar stress along various paths to draw conclusions on the effect of traction free surfaces. However, this was only a small fraction of the data that was available from the simulations that were performed. Also, other researchers would likely look at the data from a different perspective and might identify behaviors that go beyond those discussed in the paper. They can do this without having to develop the computational tools required to perform the analysis. Furthermore, visualizing the stress contours or other data at various locations on the mesh can give an investigator a feel for the behavior of the laminate that is difficult to describe in a paper without the use of more figures than would be permissible. Therefore, by providing the models and results for this investigation, collaborators can perform their own independent interpretation of results without the need for the time consuming steps of constructing models and running the analysis. In general, the availability of models can allow for collaborators to experiment with various boundary conditions or material systems with relative ease.

Figure 5. Possible weave architectures for finite element modeling

Figure 6. Free edge/free surface unit cell for symmetrically stacked plain weave

The archive will eventually contain short notes on findings that were judged to be of insufficient significance or depth of study to appear in a journal paper, but which could

be helpful to others trying to understand the behavior of textile composites and such notes might provide stimuli for future work.

The archive will also contain data that is available elsewhere, but is collected in the archive for convenience. For example, a constituent material database will be maintained. This will be a collection of material properties (and references) from the literature for tows and matrix constituents. This material database will contain both thermoelastic and strength properties. Properties for fibers will also be included for use in simulations of arrays of fibers to predict tow properties. Finally, effective thermomechanical properties of various weaves will be included. Another example is a list of publications by our research group on textile composites. The hope is that other groups will do likewise, since such collections will expedite staying up to date on the expanding textile composites literature.

Contributions by Texas A&M will evolve as more investigations on textile composite behavior are completed and we identify the type of data that is of interest to others.

Institut National des Sciences Appliquées, Lyon

This section concerns the deformation of a dry textile composite reinforcement. Especially in the first stage of a Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process the achievement of a double curved shape can be obtained by the deformation of an initially flat fibrous reinforcement. Mesoscopic simulations (i.e. simulation at the scale of the woven cell) have different applications. They give the geometry of the solid skeleton that is used by flow algorithms to evaluate permeability tensors for various geometrical configurations [19]. They can also be used as virtual tests to estimate the mechanical behaviour of the fabric at the macroscopic level without performing experimental tests [20, 21]. The deformed shape could also be used for damage initiation within the composite with the deformed reinforcement.

The example presented in Figure 7 and Table 1 is the in-plane shear of a 2 x 2 carbon twill unit cell. The shear angle is large (40°) but this is a value that can be reached in a forming process since the shear strains are the main deformation mode for a textile to achieve a double curved shape. The specific mechanical behaviour due to the fibrous nature of the yarn is modeled using a hypoelastic law with an objective derivative based on the rotation of the fibre [21, 22]. The transverse strains are large due to the weak rigidity of the yarn in the transverse section. In this plane, the “spheric” and deviatoric part of the strain representing respectively the change in fiber density and the change of shape are separated in the model. Assuming a transversal isotropy the transverse behaviour is modeled using 4 constants. The influence of the tension in the yarn direction is taken into account since a stretched fibrous tow is stiffer in the transverse plane. More details can be found in [21, 22] and the archive web site (especially the input data of the computation). The validation of the computed deformed geometry by X-ray tomography is made in [22].

Figure 7. Simulation of 40° shear of the 2x2 twill with iso-values of the compaction of fibres

Table 1. 2x2 carbon twill weave: Dimensions and mechanical properties

Weaving	2 x 2 twill	Densities (Yarn/mm)		Warp: 0,35 Weft: 0,35
Yarn width (mm)	Warp: 2,4 Weft: 2,4	Crimp (%)		Warp: 0,3 Weft: 0,35
Young modulus in the fiber direction (MPa)	98800			
	$\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} = 0.01$	$\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} = 0.05$	$\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} = 0.10$	$\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} = 0.20$
Transverse Young moduli (MPa)	5	34	420	62160
Transverse shear modulus (MPa)	1.4	10	122	18100
Longitudinal shear moduli (MPa)	20			

University of Nottingham

The submission from the University of Nottingham presently contains all of the files required to perform an Abaqus analysis for a composite manufactured from Vetrotex RT600 plain-woven glass fabric. Approximate geometric parameters of the textile are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Approximate geometric parameters of RT600 plain-woven glass fabric

Parameter	RT600
Areal density, S_0 (kg m ⁻²)	600
Tow linear density, ρ_t (tex)	1200
Tow width, w_t (mm)	3.0
Tow height, h_t (mm)	0.25
Tow spacing (pitch), s_t (mm)	4.0

Fibre volume fraction is assumed to vary across the tow according to a quadratic distribution which approximates the findings of Koissin [23]. Fibre volume fraction also changes along the length of the yarn as the cross section changes while the amount of fibre remains constant. The resulting distribution of V_f is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Contour showing the distribution of V_f both along and across yarns

These geometric data and the V_f distribution are encapsulated in the textile model, which can be loaded directly into TexGen, the University of Nottingham's open source textile modeller. TexGen was used in conjunction with Abaqus/CAE to produce finite element models. Further details of the analyses conducted can be found in [24]; a copy of this paper accompanies the material in the archive. The files uploaded provide all of the data necessary to replicate the elastic analysis of this composite, and also include the Abaqus results database. In due course, further data should be provided showing geometric measurements obtained using microscopy, results from voxel modelling, as well as experimental test data.

Osaka University

Various types of textile structures have been determined by WiseTex [6]. If the penetrations between fiber-bundles occur, the algorithm of scaling down for section area will be applied to eliminate them and will generate the FE model. The finite element mesh of composites has also been generated by putting the elements corresponding to matrix around fiber-bundles. The software named MeshTex can process them as shown in Figure 9 [8].

Figure 9. FE models of various types of textile structures and their composites

FE model of a stitched yarn with knot and NCF with a stitch can be created by WiseTex and MeshTex. Figure 10 shows the numerical results which have been analyzed by SACOM [25].

The analysis used a superposition method, because the mesh does not generate with simple procedure [26]. NCF is made of [45/-45] laminate of T700/epoxy and V_f is 42.9%. The stitched yarn is made of PES/epoxy and V_f is 22%. The finite element meshes, the analysis results, and experimental data for these configurations will be provided at the archive.

Figure 10. The numerical results of NCF with stitched yarn

CONCLUSION

This paper describes initial efforts at extending the publication paradigm. Traditional journal papers are valuable resources, but the complexity of many of the studies being conducted on textile composites mandates an enhanced venue for sharing results. A simple web based archive, The Textile Composites Archive, has been initiated which offers the opportunity to share extensive details about research efforts. Details of this archive will evolve over time, but the need for this type of enhanced information transfer is only expected to grow.

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